

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE POSSIBILITY OF RECOMPOSING A LATIN AMERICAN PATRIOTISM IN THE 21ST CENTURY.

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Abstract

In this article, we investigate the meaning of patriotism in the 21st century, particularly in Latin America, and ask if it is possible to reconstruct a Latin American patriotism that embraces the diversity of the region. We thus intend to reflect on the role that patriotism represents today and identify its influence in society and politics. The authors argue that patriotism plays an important role in society and politics. It can foster unity and a sense of community, as well as promote positive values such as respect and tolerance. The methodology we apply is qualitative: location, compilation and processing of written sources, reading and analysis of them. As first findings, we were able to observe that it is important that patriotism is based on shared values and not on exclusion or discrimination. In conclusion, the recomposition of Latin American patriotism is a process that requires time and effort. However, it is an important objective, since it can contribute to the construction of a more united and prosperous Latin American community.

Keywords: Latin America, Patriotism, politics, society, values.

Introduction.

In work we address the topic Recomposing a Latin American Patriotism that implies a feeling of pride and belonging to the Latin community. The author clippings that we use to analyze this topic are: Rufino Blanco Fombona, J. Francisco Silva and Manuel Ugarte To rebuild the patriotism of the region, it is necessary to promote greater knowledge and understanding of history and culture. The recovery of continental patriotism by these writers of the early 20th century is an important step in the formation of the national consciousness of Latin America. We delve into the work of Marcos Mele to meet Rufino Blanco-Fombona and J. Francisco V. Silva, who collaborated to dismantle the dominant historiographical story in the context of Argentina during the first Centennial.

Investigation.

In Venezuela, the figure of Rufino Blanco-Fombona began to be valued in 1974, on the occasion of his 100th birthday, his remains were transferred to the country's National Pantheon, and in these years the re-issue of some of his books began. Meanwhile, in Argentina Melé adds that figure and Manuel Ugarte are recovered by Roberto Galasso¹⁹ in 1970 who had been imagined by the official culture.

"...Blanco-Fombona who declared not to write for the "four cats" of his country but for all of Latin America. Unfortunately, Francisco Silva's work did not suffer the same fate since his books were never republished and have been transformed into practically unfindable bibliographical pieces..." (Marcos Mele 2023-8)

¹⁹ Norberto Galasso was born in Buenos Aires, in 1936. He studied at the San Martín Commercial School and at the Faculty of Economic Sciences of the UBA from where he graduated with the title of National Public Accountant, Researcher, journalist, politician, activist, ... In 1963, he published his first book Mariano Moreno and the National Revolution. Starting in 1966, he began his research work with a biography titled *Discépolo y su tiempo*, edited by Jorge Álvarez, and thus began his militancy activity by joining the Socialist Party of the National Left led by Jorge Abelardo Ramos where he established close relationships. policies with Arturo Jauretche and Juan José Hernández Arregui. ... In 1973, he served, for a few months, as trustee at the Editorial Universitaria of Buenos Aires, then directed by Arturo Jauretche. Continuing an already developed journalistic career in various print media, he collaborated with *Crisis* magazine. During the last Military Dictatorship (which censored his books "Life of Manuel Ugarte" and "What is National Socialism?") he took refuge in research and published articles abroad in the clandestine

press. Once democracy was restored, he published several works in the Political Library of the Latin American Publishing Center; among which it is worth mentioning...Galasso has published more than fifty titles -many with several reissues-, including essays, anthologies, historical-political studies, investigations and controversies. Among them, three stand out, without a doubt the most encouraging, which have required sustained efforts over recent years, and which have earned him notable recognition. It's about Let's be free and the rest doesn't matter at all. Life of San Martín, From the Baring Bank to the IMF. History of Argentina's foreign debt, and the documented two-volume biography of Perón. Today, the History of Argentina is added to these true pillars of Argentine historiography. Simultaneously with his work as a publicist, Galasso has dedicated efforts to the organization of political and cultural groups. Librería Hernández available :<https://www.libreriahernandez.com/autores/fichaAutor?authorId=39004>

Rufino Blanco-Fombona²⁰

Rufino Blanco-Fombona was born in Caracas, Venezuela, on June 17, 1874. He began his studies in law and philosophy at the Central University of Venezuela, but abandoned them to enter the Military Academy, he went into exile in Europe, where he lived during the most of his life. His work is imbued with a deep social and political commitment. Social commitment was manifested in his criticism of the dictatorship of Cipriano Castro and Juan Vicente Gómez, as well as in his defense of the rights of workers and minorities, while his political commitment was manifested in opposition to European imperialism and in his defense of the sovereignty of Latin American countries.

Being the governor of the Amazonas Federal Territory in 1905, he protected the indigenous people from the oppression to which they were subject.

"...I protected the Indians, a hundred times more intelligent, good and hard-working than the bandits who, calling themselves rational, exploit and harass them; I declared that debts do not enslave the Indian to the debtor, according to the infamous custom there..." (Marcos Mele.2023-11).

While in Europe he became concerned about the vindication of the Liberator Simón Bolívar, and in 1915 he founded Editorial América for the dissemination of books by European and Ibero-American authors to contribute to American culture and he died in Buenos Aires on October 16, 1944.

Francisco Silva.

Moving forward in reading Marcos Mele we come to Francisco Silva, born in Córdoba, Argentina, in 1893. He studied Law at the Central University of Spain, where he graduated in 1914 with a thesis on the modern concept of the State promoting the social dimension.

"...A humanitarian, civilized State, that leads a pacifist life, a State conscious of social reality..." (Marcos Mele 2023-16)

The author describes that throughout the 1910s, Silva had an active participation in different Spanish academic institutions, such as the Royal Geographical Society of Madrid and the Royal Academy of History. He also published various articles in the Madrid magazine *Comunicaciones*. In 1918, Silva published *The Liberator Bolívar and the Deán Funes* in Argentine politics, in this work, he participates in the controversy started by Blanco-Fombona over the history written by

Miter and his followers, he praises Bolívar and the federal leaders, he criticizes the British intervention in the division of Spanish America. In this book, Silva reviewed Argentine history from a Hispanic perspective, questioning the traditional view that he considered Independence as a process of rupture with Spain.

We can divide Silva's work into:

His legal work, which focuses on the study of the concept of the State and the theory of law, is important for two reasons. Firstly, because he contributes to the development of legal theory in Argentina. Secondly, because it reflects the intellectual concerns of Silva, who was interested in the role of the State in society.

Silva's thesis on the modern concept of the State was one of the first works in Argentina that adopted a sociological perspective of the State. Silva maintains that the State is a social institution that arises from the need to organize society.

His historical work, which focuses on the study of Argentine history from a Hispanist perspective, Silva's historiographic perspective, questioned the traditional vision of Independence. He also wrote about Hipólito Yrigoyen emphasizing the popular and nationalist character of Yrigoyen's triumph against the anti-personalist opposition.

We could say that Silva identified with some of Yrigoyen's actions in matters of foreign policy since he maintained a neutral position during the First World War, and advocated equality between nations. He also promoted regional integration, and supported the creation of the League of Nations.

Manuel Ugarte²¹.

From the preliminary study of López María Pía in Manuel Ugarte we can briefly analyze his life and work. He was born in Buenos Aires, came from a family of the rural bourgeoisie, received a privileged education, studied at the National College of Buenos Aires, and then moved to Paris to continue his studies, there he became involved in the socialist movement. He also became interested in Latin American culture, and began writing about the history and literature of the region.

Ugarte returned to Argentina and became an active defender of Latin American unity. In 1903, he published his book *The Future of Latin America*, in which he argued that Latin American countries should join forces to face the challenges of the modern era. After 8 years he undertakes a journey that lasts 2 years through

²⁰ El Nido del Cuco 15-02-2019 available: : <https://www.elnidodelcuco.com.ar/2019/02/15/rufino-blanco-fombona/>

²¹ Manuel Ugarte 1903 available : <http://centrougarte.unla.edu.ar/manuel-ugarte/pages/biografia.html>

Latin America and recounts what he has seen in his book *The Destiny of a Continent*. He returned to Argentina in 1913, and people expressed disinterest in him and his political action. They suspended him from the Socialist Party, which was going through a difficult period. Furthermore, in the First War he assumed naturalness.

"...But, my homeland, is it perhaps the neighborhood in which I live, the house in which I stay, the room in which I sleep? "Do we have no more flag than the shadow of the bell tower?..." (López María Pía 2010-16).

Some of the important themes of Ugarte's work are:

Latin American unity: Ugarte believed that Latin American countries should join forces to face the challenges of the modern era. In his book *The Future of Latin America*, he argued that Latin American countries shared a common history, culture, and destiny.

Social justice: Ugarte was a defender of the rights of workers and the poor. In his book *La patria grande*, he criticized the social and economic injustice that existed in Latin America.

Latin American culture: Ugarte was proud of Latin American culture, and he worked to promote its dissemination. In his book *La argentinidad*, he defended Argentine culture as an expression of Latin American culture in general.

"...Manuel Baldomero Ugarte can be called the first Creole socialist and one of the most advanced historical revisionists in Latin America. A tireless activist for continental unity, he was one of the most important Latin American thinkers of his time..." (Ugarte Manuel 2023-5).

His work has had a great influence on Latin American political and cultural thought. Ugarte continued to travel and write until his death on December 2, 1951. He is considered one of the most important intellectuals in the history of Latin America.

Patriotism today means...

The homeland is an expression of the human community, which is manifested in the nation. In this sense, the homeland is the highest level of social reality, since it represents the union of individuals around a common project.

The origin of the homeland dates back to ancient times, when the Greeks and Romans spoke of the "terra patria", the land of the fathers. At that time, the homeland was understood as the community of the inhabitants of the same city-state.

Currently, the homeland is understood as the nation, which is a sovereign political community that shares a common territory, history and culture. The nation is a social construction, but that does not make it any less real. Human memory is selective, and that means that the past reaches us with a load of myths and legends. However, these myths and legends are not false, but are part of the nation's identity. Patriotism, love for one's country, is a feeling that manifests itself in times of glory, but also in difficult times. Patriotism is an expression of the human need to belong to a community. The homeland is a complex social construction

that transcends ideologies. It is made up of three fundamental elements:

- A historical dimension: the shared past of a people, their struggles, their achievements and their failures.

- A territorial dimension: the physical space that houses that town.

- A symbolic dimension: elements that represent the homeland, such as the flag, the anthem or national heroes.

From a rational perspective, these elements may seem insignificant. However, it is the feeling of the people that gives them special value. It is the feeling of belonging, pride and solidarity that transforms a piece of cloth into a flag and a song into an anthem.

Patriotism is a universal feeling that can be experienced by people of all social classes, ideologies and beliefs. It is not a question of ideology, but of feeling. Therefore, the homeland is not a particularity, but a symbolic space that houses all citizens, regardless of their differences. It is a place where we share a past and build a future together. (La Nación 2002).

The role of citizens as an essential part when it comes to rebuilding Patriotism in the Region is also evident from what has been said " *the idea of active citizenship, which not only refers to belonging to a State as an organization, but also to the status that is defined by the rights and duties of citizen*" (Pérez Gamón Carolina 2023-799)

Findings.

The relationship of Patriotism with the idea of a group Ugarte believed that Latin American countries should join forces to face the challenges of the modern era, with which patriotism is an expression of the human need to belong to a community.

As we also observe that rebuilding Latin American Patriotism implies promoting the common values that the region shares. This can be achieved by promoting education about history and culture, making known the thoughts and actions carried out by these men who promoted dialogue and cooperation between countries, thus giving citizens a sense of belonging.

Conclusions.

The recomposition of Latin American patriotism is a process that requires time and effort on the part of society and politics. However, it is an important goal as it can contribute to building a united and prosperous community. Blanco Fomona portrays the social reality of his time, showing the misery and inequality that the poorest suffered. His work is a denunciation of corruption and injustice, and a call to action to build a more just society.

Francisco V. Silva created intellectual spaces and political-historiographic ideas between Argentina and Spain, proclaimed the union of the Hispanic peoples. Despite his clear historical opposition, Silva did not abandon the institutional spaces of his time nor did he abandon his participation in that region.

Ugarte was an important figure in the history of Latin America. His work continues to be relevant today, and his legacy continues to inspire Latin Americans fighting for social justice, culture, and promoting unity in the region.

Here are some examples of how Latin American Patriotism can manifest itself in the 21st century through: support for common causes, such as the fight against poverty or the defense of the environment, working together to promote peace and regional cooperation, as well as also the recognition of Latin American cultural diversity.

We can conclude by saying that Patriotism is a substantial part of the identity of Latin Americans, it helps define who they are and what unites them, and it also has the potential to be a positive force for change. However, it is important that it is developed in a way that is inclusive and respectful of diversity.

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